

Electrochemical Studies of some 2-Amino-4-(2'-methylphenylamino)-6-methyl-5-arylazopyrimidines

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The importance of the knowledge of the redox behaviour and $E_{1/2}$ of compounds of physiological and medicinal importance is well-known. The pyrimidines chosen for the present studies are those containing arylazo group at position-5, the latter grouping being important in promoting potential antineoplastic activity¹. Attempt was, therefore, made to study the redox behaviour of the so far uninvestigated 2-amino-4-(2'-methylphenylamino)-6-methyl-5-arylazopyrimidines (1; R = H, 2''-OC₂H₅, 3''-Cl, 4''-NO₂).

Results and Discussion

Polarograms of 2-amino-4-(2'-methylphenylamino)-6-methyl-5-arylazopyrimidines (1) were recorded in the pH

Fig. 1. Polarograms of 2-amino-4-(2'-methylphenylamino)-6-methyl-5-arylazopyrimidines: (1) R = H, (2) R = 2''-OC₂H₅, (3) 3''-Cl and (4) 4''-NO₂.

TABLE 1-POLAROGRAPHIC REDUCTION POTENTIALS OF 2-AMINO-4-(2'-METHYLPHENYLAMINO)-6-METHYL-5-ARYLAZOPYRIMIDINES AT DIFFERENT pH

Subst.	pH					
	2.5	4.5	6.5	7.5	9.5	12.0
H	0.28	0.36	0.58	0.76	0.80	0.82
2''-OC ₂ H ₅	0.53	0.66	0.86	0.96	0.91	0.90
3''-Cl	0.36	0.62	0.84	0.86	0.87	0.84
4''-NO ₂	0.70 ^b	0.42 ^b	0.40 ^b	0.42 ^b	1.02 ^a	1.04 ^a
		0.80	0.92	1.10	1.11	1.00 ^c

^aReduction of Cl group; ^breduction of NO₂ group; ^cboth waves merged.

range 2.0–12.0 (Fig. 1). Electrochemical characteristics are given in Table 1. All compounds displayed a single well-defined polarographic wave in the entire pH range studied, whereas in the case of nitro and chloro substituted compounds one additional wave has realised. The height of the wave was practically constant throughout the pH range. The nature of the wave was investigated through the dependence of limiting current on the height of mercury column. The limiting current was found to be diffusion-controlled² as evident by the linear plots of i_d vs $h^{1/2}$ (Table 2). The shift of $E_{1/2}$ towards more negative potential with increasing concentration of depolariser and logarithmic analysis confirmed the irreversible nature² of the electrode process.

TABLE 2-EFFECT OF HEIGHT OF MERCURY RESERVOIR ON THE LIMITING CURRENT OF 2-AMINO-4-(2'-METHYLPHENYLAMINO)-6-METHYL-5-ARYLAZOPYRIMIDINE

h cm	$h^{1/2}$ cm	i_d μA
50	7.07	0.80
55	7.41	0.84
60	7.74	0.88
65	8.06	0.96
70	8.36	1.08

The $E_{1/2}$ shifted towards negative potential with increase in pH of the solution. The plots of $E_{1/2}$ vs pH are linear upto pH 8.0 thereafter, there is a little change in $E_{1/2}$. A comparison of the limiting current indicates that most of the compounds are reduced by consuming the same number of electrons. Number of electrons involved in the electrode process was found to be two by coulometry.

In the case of 4''-nitro substituted compound there was an additional 4e diffusion-controlled, irreversible wave at less negative potential. The wave was found due to the reduction of nitro group and in 3'-chloro substituted pyrimidine a 2e wave was realised at more negative potential. The wave was found to be diffusion-controlled and irreversible in nature.

Controlled potential electrolysis of the parent compound at the plateau potential of 1.1 V using the mercury pool cathode consumed 2.0 electrons. The colour of the starting material faded out at the end of the electrolysis. Polarograms of the reduced solution did not give any polarographic wave. This clearly indicates that no electroactive species remained in solution after electroreduction.

The value of αn_a (the product of transfer coefficient and number of electrons involved per molecule) and p (number of protons involved per molecule) in the rate-determining step were calculated using the expressions,

$$\alpha n_a = -0.0517/(E_{1/4} - E_{3/4})$$

$$p = d E_{1/2}/dpH (\alpha n_a / 0.0591)$$

Cyclic voltammograms of 2-amino-4-(2'-methylphenylamino)-6-methyl-5-arylazopyrimidines and its 3''-Cl, 4''-NO₂, 2''-OC₂H₅ derivatives were recorded at GC, Pt and TFM electrodes in aqueous as well as non-aqueous media and voltammetric characteristics are presented in Tables 3 and 5. The electrochemical behaviour have been discussed under GC and Pt and TFM electrodes. Typical voltammograms are given in Fig. 2. At GC and Pt electrodes the voltammograms were recorded at various scan rates (50–200 mV s⁻¹) in the pH range 2.0–12.0, which exhibited one reduction peak at GC and Pt electrodes for all the compounds. For 4''-nitro substituted pyrimidine one more wave at less negative potential was observed. The reduction peak was irreversible and diffusion-controlled in

Fig. 2. Cyclic voltammograms of 2-amino-4-(2'-methylphenylamino)-6-methyl-5-arylazopyrimidines: (1) R = H, (2) R = 2''-OC₂H₅, (3) R = 3''-Cl and (4) R = 4''-NO₂; pH = 11.5, $\nu = 50$ mV s⁻¹.

nature. The peak was realised due to the reduction of NO₂ on the aryl ring.

The cathodic peak potential of the peak for the reduction of azo group shifted towards more negative potential with increasing scan rates as expected for irreversible electron transfer step. In the reverse scan no corresponding peak was observed indicating towards the irreversible nature of the peak. The plots of i_p vs $\nu^{1/2}$ are straight-lines passing

through origin, indicating diffusion-controlled³ nature of the electrode process. Furthermore, the effect of change of concentration of these compounds on diffusion current has been examined. The plot of i_p vs concentration is also a straight-line indicating towards the diffusion controlled nature of the process. The plot of E_p vs pH is linear upto 8.2 and after that there is a little change. However, for 3''-chloro substituted azopyrimidine one additional $2e$ wave at more negative potential than for reduction of the azo group, was observed. The wave was found to be irreversible and diffusion-controlled on the basis of usual criteria. For 4''-nitro derivative one more $4e$ wave was observed at less negative potential than for the reduction of azo group. On the basis of the number of electrons involved in the electrode process and comparing the peak heights and E_p values with the unsubstituted azopyrimidine which does not bear a nitro group under similar experimental condition, it was concluded that the $4e$ peak is due to the reduction of nitro group. The peak potentials show shift towards negative potential with pH. On reversing the first scan no anodic peak could be observed, indicating the second peak to be irreversible. However, in the reverse and subsequent scan a reversible redox couple (-0.38 to -0.40) corresponding to oxidation of arylhydroxylamine and reduction of the resulting nitroso compound was observed⁴, but no other peak even at higher sweep rates (250 mV s⁻¹), could be observed.

Taking in consideration various sites of reduction present in these molecules, the $-N=N-$ group is most susceptible⁵ to reduction. It has been reported⁶ that reduction of azo compounds takes place in a $2e$ -wave at the $-N=N-$ group giving the hydrazo derivative. Nygard⁷ reported $2e$ reversible reduction of azobenzene at low concentrations and pH. The irreversible nature of observed peak in compounds may be attributed to the bulky pyrimidine substituent present in the molecule. At thin film mercury electrode, 2-amino-4-(2'-methylphenylamino)-6-methyl-5-arylazopyrimidines in the pH range 2.0–12.0 gave a $2e$ reduc-

TABLE 3—VALUES OF PEAK POTENTIAL FOR THE REDUCTION OF 2-AMINO-4-(2'-METHYLPHENYLAMINO)-6-METHYL-5-ARYLAZOPYRIMIDINES AT GLASSY CARBON ELECTRODE AT DIFFERENT pH

Subst.	pH					
	2.5	4.5	6.5	7.5	9.5	11.5
H	0.31	0.35	0.38	0.42	0.59	0.63
2''-OC ₂ H ₅	0.32	0.36	0.42	0.58	0.62	0.66
3''-Cl	0.25	0.29	0.31	0.35	0.36	0.39
				0.80	0.84	0.93
4''-NO ₂	0.32	0.32	0.36	0.38	0.45	0.45
	0.62	0.66	0.68	0.80	0.88	0.88

tion peak and a small bump at less negative potential. The $2e$ peak has been assigned to the reduction of the $-N=N-$ group. The voltammograms were recorded at various scan rates ($50\text{--}200\text{ mV s}^{-1}$).

TABLE 4—EFFECT OF CONCENTRATION OF DEPolariser ON THE RATIO OF ADSORPTION RESPONSE TO DIFFUSION RESPONSE AT TFM ELECTRODE FOR 2-AMINO-4-(2-METHYLPHENYLAMINO)-6-METHYL-5-ARYLAZOPYRIMIDINE AT pH 4.5

Concn 10^{-4} M	i_c/i_c
1.0	0.42
2.0	0.39
3.0	0.34
4.0	0.31
5.0	0.29

The peak potential of the voltammograms shifted towards more negative potential with increasing scan rate, indicating the irreversible nature⁸ of the electrode process. The plots of i_p vs $\nu^{1/2}$ and i_p vs concentration were linear, indicating the diffusion-controlled nature of the electrode process³. The bump at less negative potential has been characterised as preadsorption peak due to the strong adsorption of product by monitoring the relative heights of adsorption response to diffusion response with increase in concentration of the depolariser (Table 4). This was further confirmed by the plots of $\nu^{1/2}$ vs ratio of adsorption peak current to diffusion peak current⁹. The deviation from the straight-line at higher scan rates points out that the reactant is weakly adsorbed and the product is strongly adsorbed.

In non-aqueous media (Fig. 3) the cathodic electrode process is in good agreement with that of the aqueous me-

Fig. 3. Cyclic voltammograms of 2-amino-4-(2-methylphenylamino)-6-methyl-5-arylazopyrimidines: (1) $R = \text{H}$, (2) $R = 2''\text{-OC}_2\text{H}_5$, (3) $R = 3''\text{-Cl}$ and (4) $R = 4''\text{-NO}_2$ in DMF at GC electrode.

TABLE 5—VOLTAMMETRIC CHARACTERISTICS OF 2-AMINO-4-(2-METHYLPHENYLAMINO)-6-METHYL-5-ARYLAZOPYRIMIDINES IN NON-AQUEOUS MEDIA AT GC, Pt AND TFM ELECTRODES FOR THE REDUCTION OF AZO GROUP

Scan rate = 50 mV s^{-1} , concn. = $5.0 \times 10^{-3}\text{ M}$

Subst.	GC	Pt	TFM
H	0.49	0.53	0.51
$2''\text{-OC}_2\text{H}_5$	0.57	0.65	0.54
$3''\text{-Cl}$	0.62	0.69	0.61
$4''\text{-NO}_2$	0.63	0.72	0.64

TABLE 6—VALUES OF n DETERMINED BY COULOMETRY OF 2-AMINO-4-(2-METHYLPHENYLAMINO)-6-METHYL-5-ARYLAZOPYRIMIDINES AT pH 6.5

Subst.	Applied potential V	Exptl. value of n
H	0.9	2.10
$2''\text{-OC}_2\text{H}_5$	0.9	2.12
$3''\text{-Cl}$	1.2	4.06
$4''\text{-NO}_2$	1.0	6.20

dia. But in the reverse scan at GC and Pt electrodes one diffusion-controlled oxidation peak was also observed. To confirm whether the peak is related to the reduction process or not, scan was initiated towards anodic side but no peak was observed. This confirms that at the oxidation peak, reduction products are undergoing oxidation.

Controlled potential electrolysis was carried out at a potential 1.0 V, slightly higher than the reduction peak, and the number of electrons involved was found to be 2.0 (Table 6) at all the electrodes. Only one product could be isolated by tlc after exhaustive electrolysis. On the basis of the observed facts, a mechanism proposed (Scheme 1) for the reduction of these compounds at various electrodes in aqueous as well as non-aqueous media.

However, at GC and Pt electrodes in non-aqueous media, the hydrazo product formed undergo oxidation leading to the formation of 1.

The solution after controlled potential electrolysis gave negative test for amino group thereby showing that after reduction of $-N=N-$ to $-NH-NH-$ further reduction to amino group is not taking place. Furthermore, the electrolysed solution did not exhibit any polarographic or cyclic voltammetric peak, thereby confirming the above

reduction mechanism. This mechanism is further supported by the work of others¹⁰.

Experimental

2-Arylhydrazono-1-(2'-methylphenylaminobutan)-1',3-dione (0.004 mol) was added to guanidine nitrate (0.004 mol). To this a mixture of 1.0 N NaOH and CH₃OH (5 ml) was added and the mixture was refluxed for 6 h. The reaction mixture was then allowed to cool overnight, and the resulting crystals were recrystallised from ethanol, (60%), m.p. 145° (Found: C, 67.50; H, 5.72; N, 26.43. C₁₈H₁₈N₆ requires: C, 67.92; H, 5.66; N, 26.41%); ν_{\max} (KBr) 3 100–3 200, 1 630–1 645, 1 600, 750–800 cm⁻¹; δ (270 MHz; (CD₃)₂SO) 2.65 (3H, CH₃), 2.70 (3H, het. CH₃), 3.5 (2H, NH₂), 7.0–8.0 (9H, ArH), 9.8 (1H, NH).

Polarographic measurement was done on a Elico CL 25 polarograph at 25 ± 1°. The capillary had a flow rate of 1.25 mg s⁻¹ mercury and drop-time 2.66 s at zero applied potential vs S.C.E. in 1.0 M KCl solution at a height of 65 cm of Hg column. pH was measured on an Elico LI-15 pH meter using glass electrode and saturated calomel electrode as reference electrode. Cyclic voltammetric study was performed on a BAS CV 27 voltammograph in connection with a digital electronic omnigraph X-Y/t recorder. A three-electrode cell was used for the purpose consisting of a glass container with a cap having holes for introducing electrodes and tubing of nitrogen gas. The reference electrode was Ag/AgCl electrode, and the auxiliary electrode a platinum wire which was put directly into the solution. Glassy carbon (GC), platinum (Pt) and thin film mercury (TFM) electrodes were used as the working electrodes. The GC and Pt electrodes were polished and washed with distilled water and electrochemically activated by sweeping to sufficiently anodic (+1.0 V) and cathodic (-1.6 V) voltage at slow sweep rates for about 15 min. The activity of the electrode was tested¹¹ using a solution of ferricyanide-ferrocyanide in 0.1 M KCl.

Stock solutions of all azopyrimidines were prepared in purified N,N-dimethylformamide (AnalaR). Britton-

Robinson¹² buffers in the pH range 2.0–12.0 were prepared in double-distilled water. For preparing the solutions for polarographic study, depolariser (1.0 ml), DMF (2.0 ml, which is necessary to prevent precipitation), KCl (1.0 ml) and the appropriate BR buffer (6.0 ml) were taken in the polarographic cell. The solution was deaerated¹³ by passing nitrogen gas for about 10 min and corrections for all residual currents were made in all cases. For the study in non-aqueous media, tetraethylammonium perchlorate was used as supporting electrolyte. The number of electrons involved in the electrode process was evaluated by coulometry and controlled potential electrolysis.

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